

Igbo Traditional Religion

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Igbo Religion, African Traditional Religion, Igbo Language, Language, African Religion, Pidgin

The Igbo people before the Advent of missionary religions, practiced an indigenous religion. There are schools of thought as to their origin. Igbo is argued to be of Hebrew origin. They are among the dominant ethnic groups in Nigeria. They are found in the five eastern states of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo. Like every African society, the Igbo people are religious. Their religious nature influences their lives. Their worldview is religious. This makes everything around them to have religious connotation. Event, happenings and human experiences have religious connotation and interpretation. In order to understand the Igbo people and their religion, one must understand their worldview. Igbo religion from time immemorial, satisfied their curiosity in their quest to give solution and meaning to their existence.

Date Range: 1800 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Igboland, South East, Nigeria

Region tags: Add the map for me using the map of Southeastern Nigeria

five eastern states of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo in Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Anthony N. O, Ekwunife. Consecration in Igbo Traditional Religion. Enugu: Snaap, 2003

– Source 2: Ugwu, Christopher, and Luke Ugwueye. African Traditional Religion: A Prolegomenon. Lagos: Merit International, 2002.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Igboland in Nigeria

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1163/157338386x00277>

Notes: Manus, Chris Ukachukwu. "The Concept of Death and the After-Life in the Old Testament and Igbo Traditional Religion" 3, no. 1 (1986)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3269644>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Igbo Religion is in contact with Christianity and Islam.

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↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is competitive. This is because the two other faiths seek to deplete the population of adherents of the Igbo Traditional Religion to their own gain.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is accommodating

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Igbo religion does not have a general process and or system for assigning religious affiliation. The traditional Igbo society is organized at the village/community level each Igbo man or woman naturally belongs to the group of worshippers of the deity in their village

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Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Igbo traditional religion does not proselytise. Members are recruited from among community members that are ready to join.

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Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Igbo religion has no official political support. The only affiliation it has with political system is the patronage the religion enjoys from the political class who may even claim not to be part of them, but consults the adherents when challenged with various degrees of problems.

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Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a sense of apostasy in the Igbo Traditional Religions.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: In traditional Igbo society, the apostates are punished. The offence committed is the determinant of the kind of punishment to be administered to the offender. The punishment may include; capital punishment, ostracize, fine, parading the person in public places such as market, etc.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are physically marked as such (e.g. branding, mutilation):
– No

↳ Apostates are executed:
– No

↳ Apostates are publicly executed:
– No

↳ Other corporal punishment:
– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: In every Igbo community, almost everyone claims to be a Christian (Christianity is more populous than Islam in Igboland). Getting the numerical strength is not very much easy. One can easily mistake some members of other religious groups to be members of Igbo religion.

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Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Igboland in Nigeria

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (actively discouraged-suppressed by larger religious group(s))

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:
– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

Notes: This is not the case.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: This does not often happen

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: The Igbo traditional religion has no scripture. There is no sacred book or writing associated with Igbo religion.

Reference: Awolalu, Omosade , and Adelumo Dopamu. West Africa Traditional Religion. Ibadan: Macmillan, 2005.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Igboland in Nigeria

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group had nice architecture that is suitable for their climatic environment.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 40

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 18

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: Tombs are not adorned in Igbo religion.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: Cemetery is for is set aside for those that die young. Any married person is buried in his compound known as obi.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Temple houses the shrine

↳ Altars:

– No

Notes: Altar may not necessarily be a wonderful architecture.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The group recognises that the body is distinct from the spirit. They understand that the spirit outlives the body and that they are separated at death.

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Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The group agrees that although the spirit cannot be seen with the physical eyes neither can it be felt or touched, it is nonetheless real.

Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: In Igbo religion, there is a belief in life hereafter. To them life is in circle. One dies, gets into the

ancestral Cult to be born into the family again. Their belief in lifeafter is in their understanding of ancestral world.

Reference: Manus, Chris Ukachukwu. "The Concept of Death and the After-life in the Old Testament and Igbo Traditional Religion" 3, no. 1 (1986). <https://doi.org/10.1163/157338386x00277>.

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↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that there are two places for the afterlife. One is the good place for good people and a place of torment and anguish. The supreme being lives in the sky while the evil one lives in a dark and scary place.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Not everyone reincarnates in the belief of Igbo religion. Those that reincarnates must have lived good life based on what the community prescribed as good living, died at old age and at death receive elaborate burial and funeral ceremonies.

Reference: Ubah, C. N.. "The Supreme Being, Divinities and Ancestors in Igbo Traditional Religion: Evidence from Otanchara and Otanzu" 52, no. 2 (April 1982). <https://doi.org/10.2307/1159143>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Igboland in Nigeria

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on status of the dead individual. The body of those that died accused death are hurriedly buried or thrown into the evil forest. But others are prepared for good burial depending on the Culture area.

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↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: During burial, some members of the deceased family will throw soil into the grave before it is covered after saying some words. Especially when it is suspected that the deceased did not die naturally.

Specific to this answer:

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Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: The in-laws bring materials such as cloth that the death is buried with.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

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↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: This depends on the personality and the family.

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

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Are formal burials present:

– Yes

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↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

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↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: This is for those that died without getting married.

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↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: There may be no family cemetery. But any available space as agreed by the family

becomes burial spot for grave to be dug.

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– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: It is not in every situation that the death is buried inside the house. This is done mostly when the death is suspected to have been killed and in order to prevent the person who killed the death having access to the grave, the death maybe buried inside the house.

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↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Igboland in Nigeria

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, human language can be used to describe the supreme being

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- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - Yes
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: He is loving, kind, faithful and benevolent.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: .esslimitl is edgeknowl his ,ngbei supremesprem het ngBei

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: He is the one who brings all things to be. The group holds that he is in charge of the entire world.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: .mfor yan act toerpow andilityab het Has
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings can be seen in the form of masquerades and in inanimate objects like hills, streams where the supernatural inhabits.

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↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Being spirit, it is not limited to time and geographical location.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal

essence):

– Yes

Notes: In Igbo religion, some Oracle at the death of the priest make choice of who to be the next priest. The knowledge of the character of humans guide the Oracle.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural being can reward. The ancestors have the potential to reward.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural being can as well punish the those that go against the norms of the society.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Igboland in Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: In Igbo religion, their world is dominated by spiritual forces. So they have direct effect on the society.

Reference: Onunwa, Udobata R.. "The Individual and Community in African Traditional Religion and Society" 34, no. 3 (1994). <https://doi.org/10.46469/mq.1994.34.3.7>.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural being has potential to exhibit positive emotions. This is done through blessing the upright in the society.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Of course, the negative emotions can be devastating. In their anger, a lineage can be wiped out.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Making someone to be poor can be one of the ways to punish the unrighteous.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: .it splease ti ywa any stmanife totentialpo eth has edivin The .edivin thesdiscusseussdisc he ,turalsuperna the abouttalks eon nWhempericalemperica oint edsubject beotcann edivin The .telycompleddcomprehen otcann man ttha edivin the withdeals turalsuperna The

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: npantheon anizedOrg

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Reference: Ugwu, Christopher, and Luke Ugwueye. African Traditional Religion: A Prolegomenon. Lagos: Merit International, 2002.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural is present in Igbo cosmology. In their worldview, man is surrounded by forces more powerful than him. This is the reason in their understanding nothing happens without a cause. For anything to happen in the physical, there must be a supernatural cause.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: The religious specialists have food taboos

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: There are sacred places in Igbo religion. Such places are: shrines, some areas of a river, stream, etc.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: There are sacred objects also. These sacred objects are some, trees, totems, materials set aside for worship. They may include: pots, stones, knife, plates, etc.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder of any kind is an abomination. Killing of fellow human being is permissible only when someone has committed an abomination. Under this circumstance, the supernatural permits killing of the person who committed an abominable act to appease the gods.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: In the past, every community in Igbo had a worship system known to them. The issue of what happened to members of other religions never arose. However, in the contemporary Igbo society that has become competitive and the campaign for Cultural revival, persons pushing for the revival can wish members of other religions evil so as to succeed.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: In Igbo religion, so far one has not done anything that deserves death such as abominable acts, such deaths are condemned.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: The earth goddess (ala) is the custodian of morality. The earth goddess does not spare married women who engage in extra marital affairs. Husbands are not affected in most cases when they engage in extra marital affairs. This is because traditional, wives are seen as the property of the man. Culturally, man are not blamed or condemned when they engage in extra marital affairs. However, husband can be affected if he knows that the wife is involved in extra marital affairs and continues to eat food prepared by the woman. Because he is aware and failed to act against the act, he dies with the first son.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: In Igbo religion, having sexual relationship with ones relation is not permissible. The act of incest is one of the most abomination in Igboland.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: .nableabomi isttha an is cticepra sexual ofpesty herot Any

Notes: Such sexual act as homosexuality, bestiality, etc is evil and abomination.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Lying is against the Igbo norms and traditions. Though some persons may manipulate the divine, but the consequences for that had always been catastrophic.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Oath is an indication that there is no mutual trust. When oath is taking, parties concerned are expected to abide by the oath. If one is guilty in case of suspicion, such individual pays for not being truthful.

Reference: Awolalu, Omosade , and Adelumo Dopamu. West Africa Traditional Religion. Ibadan: Macmillan, 2005.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: In Igbo religion that everything has religious implication, the divine is also interested in dignity of labour. In their culture in nurturing of the child, dignity for labour is highly emphasized. This means that laziness is abhorred. Such individuals are called the efulefu (never do well).

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is an important aspect of Igbo religion. The diviners who are among the are essential religious personalities used the medium of sorcery to interact with the supernatural behalf of those that consult him for solution to their problems.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Respect for elders are highly demanded and as well appreciated. This is the reason for including it in their child's training. Disrespect for elders is seriously condemned and indication that a child has not been properly nurtured.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Gossip in Igbo religion is not so much a serious case because when it is not damning. More over, gossip in Igbo Culture is associated with the female folk. The male folk is believed to be busy always and therefore has to time for gossiping. However, anything that impends on the communal nature of the community cannot be encouraged by the gods.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Crime of any kind is not condoned in Igbo religion. Property crime may include, stealing of property and claim of one that does not belong to the person. In most cases, the supernatural is consulted to find out the real owner of the property in contention. When.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals are very important in Igbo religion. Through rituals, human being maintain contact and Communion with the supernatural. The day begins with ritual, as the family head performs ritual with the kolanut to consult the ancestors and the gods before the activities of the day begins.

Reference: Jude Emeka, Madu. *Honest to African Cultural Heritage*. Onitsha: Coskan, 2004.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Notes: Igbo religion is not a missionary religion. So the supernatural being is not concerned with conversion. It is a religion that is naturally converting people. One should not be surprised with the high level of call for Cultural revival in Igboland which is mainly on the belief aspect of the Igbo Culture.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Notes: It may not be necessary to enforce religious ritual. It is done to punish one for offense committed.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: If the norms are not protected the society will experience anarchy. Punishing offenders serves as a deterrent to those with criminal traits and the society is preserved.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done randomly:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: This is not highly emphasised. Much emphasis is on the implications of living life which will make one not to enter into the ancestral world for reincarnation.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: The Igbo myth has that the person is giving a razor to cut an iroko tree. Iroko tree in Igbo society is very big and tall. The punishment is not believed to be mild.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: In Igbo religion, part of the punishment is to reincarnate in lesser being as earthworm, centipede and millipede.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: It pertinent to note that the political system is grontological system. The man who commits an abomination is punished through death.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: Drought and crop failure is an indication that an angry god is at work and once it has been established to be so through divination, the god is appeased.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Everything that happens in Igbo religion has spiritual implications. Therefore, no punishment is seen as being mild.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

Notes: Sickness in Igbo religion is caused by the supernatural forces. Germ theory has no place in Igbo worldview. For to be sick means that the person must have offended some spirit. The cause and solution must be sort for to save the person from more calamity.

Reference: Anyanwu Herbert O.. African Traditional Religion from the Grassroots. Uyo: Saviour, 2004.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes

Notes: Misfortunes in family may be attributed to how their father lived his life. Eg, in some families that their fathers were diabolical and used their diabolical inclination to kill people, members of such families die premature and do not progress in life.

↳ Other [specify]
– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

Notes: Every agency is involved in rewarding man.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Done randomly:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– No

Notes: The supernatural reward is both now and in the hereafter.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

Notes: The supernatural reward is also in the hereafter, but begins in lifetime.

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: No pleasure is mild and or extreme.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: This is very important for the continuation of lineage. When the god of fecundity is offended, it can manifest in negatively in the reproduction process. p

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: Messianic beliefs are not present in Igbo religion.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is social norm known as omenala/omenani. However, what constitutes the tradition and custom may vary from one Igbo society to the other. But these norm that came to be as the need arose is to ensure morally and society order vertical and horizontal relationships.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Notes: The norms are strong and has consequences when violated.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, someone's misfortune may be attributed to the lifestyle.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Notes: Moral norms have connection with the metaphysical.

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Celibacy applies to certain religious personalities and purely to allow for total dedication and service to the gods.

Reference: Anthony N. O, Ekwunife. Consecration in Igbo Traditional Religion. Enugu: Snaap, 2003.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: It does not require such. Where and when required, it is a religious obligation by the supernatural being.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Every male is expected to be productive so as to reproduce. Such religious duty is not required of the members of Igbo religion. Where celibacy is required, the supernatural does the selection.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is not official requirement in Igbo religion. Except for some religious personalities who are required to fast.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Certain foods may be a taboo for a reason and varies from Society to society. Again, religious personalities may be required to observe food taboo by the gods. This may be for spiritual alertness and efficacy of their office.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: It does not require such.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Such is not expected of members in Igbo religion.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: People are expected to having time for religious and social activities

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: But not in every case and circumstance. However, in time of emergency such as war, able bodied men are expected to take risk to save their community from the attack of their enemies.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: For anyone it is demanded of.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Marginalization is personal and when demanded of one by the society.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no specific number of time.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Gin and some other local intoxicants are use freely in Igbo religion.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: The society to which Igbo religion belongs is better described as a tribe. Though people with dialectical differences but with common central language.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: There are no institutionalized famine relief system. However, The people had a system through their communal practice to ensure that none lacks basic things of life. One does glory in seeing the relation suffer.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No such thing existed. Rather in some Igbo communities after harvesting of the crops, whatever remains is left for the indigent members of the society.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: There is no such arrangement.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: The communal nature of the Igbo people makes it obligatory for every family to take care of elderly and infirm in their midst. The necessary of child bearing with is highly cherished is to have people that can take care of one at old age.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No formal education existed in Igbo religion. Infact, what is seen as informal was their formal education. Education was acquired from the family and every adult members of the society.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There were institution which helped in training people to acquire knowledge needed in the society. These institutions are the family, age grade, umuada (daughters in a family), cults like masquerade cult, and so on.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The bureaucracy is of the supernatural; the elders and elders in council and religious persons such as the priests, medicine men, rain makers are groups or institutions that necessary for the governance of the Igbo society.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Everything has religious implications and therefore interacts with institutions to main undisconnected relationship with the supernatural.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: There was no public food storage system. Every family made provision on how to preserve food.

Some of the foods were smoked in the kitchen the the cause of cooking. Tubers like yam are kept in a place prepared for the preservation.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No such provision is made.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: However, flooding as it is experienced now was not witnessed in Igbo society. This is because they had thatched houses that did not encourage flooding. Again, irrigation system was not practiced the way it is done today. But they had water management system where they had ground dug to harvest water for use during dry season.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water is managed by age grade charged with such responsibility.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: There was no transportation except walk by the foot.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: The Igbo traditional religion has no idea about tithe. However, levy is demanded from the men when the need arose. Communities also organize communal work to keep the community clean.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There was no such thing as taxes, but communities gave themselves levies to take care of their need.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: There was no such. Cases can be looked into at various levels such as the family, age grade, umuada and council of elders.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Punishment follow the tradition of the people.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: This because there was no formal judicial system.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No such thing was in existence.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Every able bodied man served in the war when the need arose.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: There is no distinct written language, though in Igbo religion the local dialect is used in the worship. Again, the language used in blessing the Igbo kolanut is Igbo language. the belief of Igbo is that kolanut does not understand any language except Igbo language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: They have their calendar which was done using the moon. Four days make a week and twenty eight days make a month.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The calendar is calculated by the chief priest and in some places by the eldest person. The days are Orié, Afor, Nkwo and Eke. Each of the days is associated to a God.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The kind of food produced depends on the environment. Foods are produced based what community is known for. For example, people who are not in Riverside cannot fish. Likewise, only communities that has forest have hunters.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Food is provided by the religious group. What constitutes food in every community depends on the kind of food available to them.

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